

Revisiting the Ether as the Medium of Light

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Abstract

We used classical mechanics to accurately calculate the angle of deflection of starlight passing around the sun. Calculating this angle begins with the assumption that the ether, the medium of light, has mass. Using observational data, we demonstrated that the angle of deflection of the starlight predicted by Einstein's theory of relativity is inconsistent with the measured values. The Michelson-Morley experiment and Einstein's theory of relativity have made the ether disappear from modern physics. If the ether has a mass, the Michelson-Morley experiment is not an appropriate experimental setup for detecting ether. We propose a new experimental method to search for ether. The experiment involved allowing two beams of light to strike a single point on the Earth's surface and measuring the interference pattern that results under different conditions. An ether with a mass can potentially explain many unresolved problems in the universe, including dark matter.

Keywords: Ether, Dark matter, Gravity, Starlight deflection angle calculation, General relativity, Michelson-Morley experiment

1. Introduction

Until the late 19th century, it was believed that light was a wave and that a medium existed for its propagation. The medium that served as light in space was called the ether. However, the Michelson-Morley experiment of 1887 concluded that ether did not exist. The basic concept of the Michelson-Morley experiment was that if the Earth was moving through the ether, which exists everywhere in the universe, the speed of light should vary depending on the direction of the Earth's motion. The Michelson-Morley experiment attempted to measure the change in the speed of light by observing the interference phenomenon that occurs when two rays of light, traveling in different directions perpendicular to the Earth's orbit, are combined. Despite numerous modifications to the conditions, interference was not measured. Therefore, it was concluded that the ether was nonexistent. [1]

Modern physics is based on the principles of quantum mechanics and relativity. Unlike Newtonian mechanics, which deals with the macroscopic world, quantum mechanics, which deals with the microscopic world at the atomic and electron levels based on Planck's constant h , and the theory of relativity, which interprets the speed of light c as a constant, are representative examples. [2] The Michelson-Morley experiment concluded that ether does not exist as one of the most important experiments that gave birth to Einstein's special theory of relativity, a field of modern physics. Einstein's special theory of relativity, published in 1905, stipulates that the speed of light is constant in all inertial frames. Therefore, ether was not necessary. The light propagates spontaneously without a medium. Regardless of the observer's speed, the observed speed of light c remains constant.

General relativity interprets the deflection of starlight passing by the sun as a result of the deflection of the massless vacuum space, which is caused by the magnitude of the gravitational field, and light propagates in the direction of this deflection. Because mass is excluded from the propagation of light, Newtonian mechanics becomes meaningless.

So far, we have explained the reasons and background for why ether, the medium of light, is no longer

needed in modern physics. The following explains why ether, the medium of light, must exist. Furthermore, we explain that the ether must possess mass to accurately explain the direction of the motion of light within a gravitational field.

2. Discrepancies Between the Observed Deflection Angles of Starlight and the Values Calculated from General Relativity

We examined the observational data of the deflection angles of the starlight passing near the sun, collected between 1917 and 1952, and compared them with the deflection angles predicted by Einstein's general theory of relativity. Here, we point out that the observational data are inconsistent with the values calculated from general relativity. Table 1 presents the observed deflection angles of the starlight measured during solar eclipses. The minimum and maximum distances denote the closest and farthest distances at which the starlight passes, respectively, relative to the center of the sun. The quantity $\theta(^{\circ})$ represents the observed deflection angle of the starlight at these distances. [3]

Observation	Date	No. of stars	Minimum distance (10 ⁹ m)	Maximum distance (10 ⁹ m)	Deflection angle ($\theta, ^{\circ}$)	Error ($^{\circ}$)
Greenwich	1919.5.29	7	1.40(2R)	4.2(6R)	1.98	0.16
		11	1.40(2R)	4.2(6R)	0.93	-
Greenwich	1919.5.29	5	1.40(2R)	4.2(6R)	1.61	0.40
A-Greenwich	1922.9.21	11 ~ 14	1.40(2R)	7.0(10R)	1.77	0.40
Victoria	1922.9.21	18	1.40(2R)	7.0(10R)	1.42	-
					1.75	-
Rik1	1922.9.21	62 ~ 85	1.47(2.1R)	10.1(14.5R)	1.72	0.15
Rik2	1922.9.21	145	1.47(2.1R)	29.4(4.2R)	1.82	0.20
Potsdam1	1929.5.9	17 ~ 18	1.05(1.5R)	5.3(7.5R)	2.24	0.10
Potsdam2	1929.5.9	84 ~ 135	2.80(4R)	10.5(15R)	-	-
Stenbeg	1936.6.19	16 ~ 29	1.40(2R)	5.0(7.2R)	2.73	0.31
Sendai	1936.6.19	8	2.80(4R)	4.9(7R)	2.13	1.15
Yekis1	1947.5.20	51	2.31(3.3R)	7.1(10.2R)	2.01	0.27
Yekis2	1952.2.25	9 ~ 11	1.47(2.1R)	6.0(8.6R)	1.70	0.10

Table 1. Observational data on the deflection angle of starlight passing the sun during a solar eclipse. [3]

Here, R is the radius of the sun, approximately 7×10^8 m. This is denoted as 1R. As shown in the table, even during a solar eclipse, the sun was too bright to be observed at a distance (1R) when the starlight passed over the sun's surface. It was observed at approximately 2R (1.4×10^9 m) to 10R (7×10^9 m). The observed starlight deflection angles ranged from 2.73" to 0.93".

The equation for calculating the deflection angle of the starlight passing through the sun, presented by Einstein in the gravitational field equations of general relativity, is as follows:

$$\theta = \frac{4GM}{Rc^2} (\text{Radian}) \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), R represents the perigee distance from the sun's center (the distance to the sun's surface), which is 7×10^8 m. Where G is the gravitational constant (6.67×10^{-11} N.m²/kg²) and M is the mass of the sun (1.99×10^{30} kg). Here, c is the speed of light (3×10^8 m/s). The angle θ of the starlight deflection, which was calculated using the Einstein equation, was 1.74" (second). (To convert radian to degrees, we multiply by $180/\pi$. To convert degree ($^\circ$) to second ("), we multiply by 3600.) However, this Einstein angle of deflection is the value when the perigee distance R, when the starlight passes through the surface of the sun, is 1R (7×10^8 m). As previously mentioned, at the perigee distance of 1R (7×10^8 m) observed during the actual solar eclipse, the surface of the sun was too bright to measure the starlight. It was measurable only at distances greater than approximately 2R (1.4×10^9 m). When the perigee distances of 2R to 10R observed at the observatory were substituted into Einstein's formula, the deflection angle was 0.87" (2R) to 0.17" (10R).

Perigee distance from the center of the sun (10^9 m)	Einstein's calculated deflection angle (θ , ")	Actually observed deflection angle (θ , ")
7.00(10R)	0.17	
3.50(5R)	0.35	0.93
2.80(4R)	0.44	~
2.10(3R)	0.56	2.73
1.40(2R)	0.87	
0.70(1R)	1.74	Unobservable

Table 2. Shows the observed and calculated deflection angles for perigee distances of 1R (7.0×10^8 m) and 2R (1.4×10^9 m) to 10R (7×10^9 m) and the deflection angles calculated using Einstein's equation.

In conclusion, Table 2 shows that the observed deflection angles at perigee distances of 2R (1.4×10^9 m) to 10R (7×10^9 m) ranged from 2.73" to 0.93", whereas the calculated angles using Einstein's Equation (1) ranged from 0.87" to 0.17", indicating that the observed values and Einstein's equation do not agree.

Even when various inputs to Einstein's equation based on the observed perigee values were applied, Einstein's equations were inconsistent with the observed values.

3. Accurately Calculating the Deflection Angle of Starlight Using Classical Mechanics

The calculation of the deflection angle of the starlight using classical mechanics was approached by acknowledging the existence of ether. The ether discussed here must possess mass to accurately calculate the starlight deflection angle. The ether acted as the medium for light. This approach is analogous to considering the waves generated on ocean surfaces. A wave, which is a bundle of kinetic energy, is transmitted through seawater, and seawater itself possesses a mass. In a similar manner to assigning mass to a unit volume of a wave, we assign mass to a unit volume of the ether—the medium of light—in order to calculate the deflection angle of the starlight. [4,5]

In Figure 1), the mass m traveling along path A→B is defined as the mass per unit volume of ether. As shown in Figure 1, each mass m travels through three paths at the same time t.

The three paths are as follows:

- A mass m moves around the sun along the path C→B at an orbital velocity v' during time t.
- A mass m, which departed from point A at the same time t, moves along path A→B at velocity v.
- A mass m, which departed from point A at the same time t, moves along the hypothetical path A→D at an angular velocity v_2 , which is the same as path C→B.

Figure 1) To determine the angle of deflection due to the gravitational field when a mass m , starting from point A, reaches point B, we establish three hypothetical segments (C→B, A→B, A→D) that move at the same time (t).

If the travel time t is the same for each location as the mass m moves along paths A→D, A→B, and C→B, the sum of the gravitational forces transmitted will be the same, unless there are any gravitational distance limits or obstacles. This is to determine the magnitude of light deflection due to the sum of the gravitational forces when a mass m , starting from point A, passes through the center of the sun at a distance r . Furthermore, we calculate the gravitational sum of mass m traveling along the three segments around the sun to determine the time t for each segment.

First, we calculate the gravitational force acting on the path A→B. The gravitational force F acting on mass m is expressed as follows: [6,7]

$$F = G \frac{Mm}{x^2+r^2} \quad (2)$$

Here, the gravitational force acting only in the direction of vector j is expressed as

$$F_j = G \frac{Mm}{x^2+r^2} \sin \theta_k = G \frac{Mmr}{(x^2+r^2)^{3/2}} \quad (3)$$

The sum of the gravitational forces acting in the direction of vector j as mass m moves a distance x along path A→B is expressed as

$$F_{jx} = \int F_j dx = G \frac{Mmx}{r\sqrt{x^2+r^2}} \quad (4)$$

Converting Equation (4) into potential energy yields Equation (5) below. This represents the sum of the potential energy acquired by mass m through the gravitational force acting in the direction of vector j as it moves a distance x along path A→B.

$$V_{jx}(r) = \int F_{jx} dr = -GMm \ln \left| \frac{x+\sqrt{x^2+r^2}}{r} \right| \quad (5)$$

Second, we calculate the sum of the gravitational forces acting toward the center of the sun as mass m moves along path $C \rightarrow B$. As shown in Figure 1, mass m shifts its direction of travel by an angle θ_ℓ from its initial direction at point C to point B . The gravitational force acting on mass m as it moves along path $C \rightarrow B$ is expressed as

$$F' = G \frac{Mm}{r^2} \quad (6)$$

The sum of the gravitational forces exerted by the sun perpendicular to the direction of mass m as it moves a distance a along path $C \rightarrow B$ is expressed as follows:

$$F'_a = \int F' da = G \frac{Mma}{r^2} \quad (7)$$

Converting Equation (7) into Potential Energy yields Equation (8). This represents the sum of the potential energy acquired by mass m as it moves a distance a along path $C \rightarrow B$, owing gravity acting perpendicular to the sun.

$$V'_a(r) = \int F'_a dr = -G \frac{Mma}{r} \quad (8)$$

We calculated the sum of the potential energy acquired while moving along paths $A \rightarrow B$ and $C \rightarrow B$ during time t . Now, we calculate the kinetic energy of uniform motion perpendicular to the direction of gravity. The kinetic energies along paths $A \rightarrow B$ and $C \rightarrow B$ are expressed as follows:

$$K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \quad (9)$$

$$K' = \frac{1}{2}mv'^2 \quad (10)$$

The sum of the individual kinetic energies can be expressed as follows:

$$K_n = \int \frac{1}{2}mv^2 dn = n \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \quad (11)$$

$$K'_n = \int \frac{1}{2}mv'^2 dn = n \frac{1}{2}mv'^2 \quad (12)$$

Mass m , which possesses kinetic energy as it moves along paths $A \rightarrow B$ and $C \rightarrow B$, tends to move in its initial direction according to the law of inertia. However, because of the potential energy exerted by gravity, it shifts its direction by θ_{half} and θ_ℓ from its initial direction. Now, let us consider the direction of the kinetic energy and the direction in which the potential energy acts. If the directions of the two energies are perpendicular to each other and the potential energy changes the initial direction of the kinetic energy owing to gravity, it can be expressed as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2) Gravitational potential energy changes the direction of kinetic energy.

On path $C \rightarrow B$, mass m experiences gravitational potential energy perpendicular to the initial direction of kinetic energy. If we know the angle θ_ℓ changed by the action of potential energy on kinetic energy when a mass m moves along a path $C \rightarrow B$ with a perigee distance r during time t , and if we know the magnitude of that change, then we can find the change in the angle θ_{half} changed by the kinetic energy and potential energy acting on the mass m moving along a path $A \rightarrow B$ with a perigee distance r at time t . This can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{V'_a(r)}{K'_n} = \theta_1 \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{V_{jx}(r)}{K_n} = \theta_{\text{half}} \quad (14)$$

Using Equations (5), (8), (11), (12), we can express this as follows:

$$\frac{V'_a(r)}{K'_n} = -\frac{2GMa}{nr^2v^2} = \theta_1 \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{V_{jx}(r)}{K_n} = -\frac{2GMm \ln \left| \frac{x+\sqrt{x^2+r^2}}{r} \right|}{nv^2} = \theta_{\text{half}} \quad (16)$$

From Equations (15) and (16), we can express the angular deflection θ_{half} as follows:

$$\theta_{\text{half}} = \theta_1 \times \frac{rv^2 \ln \left| \frac{x+\sqrt{x^2+r^2}}{r} \right|}{av^2} \quad (17)$$

We can calculate the angle of deflection of any starlight passing through a planet or star using Equation (17), provided we know the mass of the planet (or star). Now, we calculate the angle of deflection of the starlight passing through the sun by inputting each variable. We calculate the angle of deflection of the starlight from the observed perigee distances of 2 to 10R. Refer to Table 1. We calculate the angle of deflection at perigee distance 2R ($r = 1.40 \times 10^9$ m). We will calculate the angle of deflection at 3R ($r = 2.10 \times 10^9$ m), 4R ($r = 2.80 \times 10^9$ m), 5R ($r = 3.50 \times 10^9$ m), and 10R ($r = 7.0 \times 10^9$ m), as described in Table 3. For reference, we also calculate the angle of deflection at 1R ($r = 7.0 \times 10^8$ m), which is not observable.

Next, we determine each variable. When a mass m orbits a path with a perigee distance of 2R ($r = 1.40 \times 10^9$ m), the orbital velocity v' is 3.08×10^5 m/s, using gravity ($F = G \frac{Mm}{r^2}$) and centrifugal force ($F = m \frac{v'^2}{r}$). $v' = 3.08 \times 10^5$ m/s. See Figure 1). To calculate the distance x , we use the fact that the time t is the same when moving along paths A→B and C→B. By applying a virtual path A→D, which has the same angular velocity as path C→B, we can calculate the time t . Here, the velocity v along path A→B is the speed of light c , and $v < v_2$. The distance along path A→D is a_2 . The distances a and a_2 travelling along path C→B and virtual path A→D can be expressed as follows.

$$a = v't = 2\pi r \frac{\theta_1}{360} \quad (18)$$

$$a_2 = v_2 t = 2\pi \sqrt{x^2 + r^2} \frac{\theta_1}{360} \quad (19)$$

Equations (18) and (19) can be expressed as follows.

$$x = r \sqrt{\left(\frac{v_2}{v'}\right)^2 - 1} = vt \quad (20)$$

From Equations (19) and (20), we can obtain the velocity v_2 of virtual path A→D.

$$v_2 = \frac{v'}{r} \sqrt{(vt)^2 + r^2} \quad (21)$$

Equation (21) can be obtained by substituting the orbital velocity v' (3.08×10^5 m/s) and perigee distance r (1.40×10^9 m).

$$v_2 = 2.2 \times 10^{-4} \sqrt{(x)^2 + r^2} \quad (22)$$

Applying Equation (22) to Equation (19) yields the following:

$$2.2 \times 10^{-4} \sqrt{(x)^2 + r^2} t = 2\pi \sqrt{x^2 + r^2} \frac{\theta_1}{360} \quad (23)$$

Here, the sum of θ_k and θ_ℓ is 90° . Comparing the distance x traveled at the speed of light c and the radius r , the distance x is significantly larger than the radius r ($r \ll x$), and therefore θ_ℓ approaches 90° ($\theta_\ell \approx 90^\circ$). Applying each variable to Equation (23) yields time t .

$$t = \frac{\pi}{2 \times (2.2 \times 10^{-4})} = 7,136.4 \text{sec} \quad (24)$$

Now, by applying the time t , we can find the distance a ($a = v't = 2.20 \times 10^9$ m) along the path $C \rightarrow B$ and the distance x ($x = vt = 2.14 \times 10^{12}$ m) along path $A \rightarrow B$. By substituting each value into Equation (17), we can find the deflection angle θ_{half} of mass m due to the action of gravity while moving along path $A \rightarrow B$. (Second)

$$\theta_{\text{half}} = 4.85 \times 10^{-4} = 1.75'' \quad (25)$$

As shown in Figure 1), mass m departs from point A and reaches the earth observer (point F) via perigee B . In Equation (25), the deflection angle θ_{half} is the deflection angle of path $A \rightarrow B$, and the deflection angle of path $B \rightarrow F$ is approximately twice the deflection angle θ_{half} under the same conditions. The final angle of deflection θ of the starlight passing through the perigee distance $2R$ ($r = 1.40 \times 10^9$ m) and observable by an observer at point F is as follows.

$$\theta = 2 \times \theta_{\text{half}} \approx 3.50'' (\text{second}) \quad (26)$$

The angle of deflection of the starlight passing around the sun is summarized in Table 3: the angle calculated using classical mechanics, the angle calculated using Einstein's formula, and the actual observed angle.

Perigee distance from the center of the sun (10^9 m)	Einstein's calculated deflection angle (θ , ")	The angle of deflection (θ , ") calculated using classical mechanics	Actually observed deflection angle (θ , ")
7.00(10R)	0.17	0.77	
3.50(5R)	0.35	1.51	0.93
2.80(4R)	0.44	1.76	~
2.10(3R)	0.56	2.40	2.73
1.40(2R)	0.87	3.50	
0.70(1R)	1.74	6.58	Unobservable

Table 3. The deflection angles of starlight passing near the sun, calculated using classical mechanics, using Einstein's formula, and those actually observed, are summarized.

The angles θ calculated using classical mechanics at perigee distances ($2R$ (1.40×10^9 m) to $10R$ (7.00×10^9 m)) during a solar eclipse are calculated to be $3.50''$ to $0.77''$, as shown in Table 3), which is almost identical to the values observed during the eclipse in Table 1. The observed angles θ of the starlight ranges from $2.73''$ to $0.93''$. The sun's angle of deflection, θ , calculated using classical mechanics at a perigee distance of $1R$ (0.70×10^9 m), which is too bright to be observed, is $6.58''$. Substituting this into Einstein's Equation (1) for perigee distances of $2R$ to $10R$ yields a range of $0.87''$ to $0.17''$. This does not match the observed value of $2.73''$ to $0.93''$. Furthermore, at an unobservable perigee distance of $1R$, the angle of deflection calculated using Einstein's equation is $1.74''$ (second), which is too small compared to the observed value.

We have accurately calculated the angle of deflection of the starlight using classical mechanics.

Conclusion: If we can accurately calculate the angle of deflection of starlight using classical mechanics as described above, we can conclude that light has a medium and that this medium has a mass.

Table 4 calculates the angle of deflection of the starlight passing around the planets and moon of the solar system for reference.

Planet	Mass (kg, M)	Radius (m, R)	Perigee distance(r)	v'(m/s)	t(sec)	a(m)	x(m)	θ_i	Deflection angle (θ_{Planet} , ")
Mercury	3.30×10^{23}	2.44×10^6	1R~10R	$3 \times 10^3 \sim 9.50 \times 10^2$	$1.28 \times 10^3 \sim 4.04 \times 10^4$	$3.84 \times 10^6 \sim 3.83 \times 10^7$	$3.84 \times 10^{11} \sim 1.21 \times 10^{13}$	$\approx 90^\circ$	$5.22 \times 10^{-4}'' \sim 5.72 \times 10^{-5}''$
Venus	4.82×10^{24}	6.05×10^6	1R~10R	$7.29 \times 10^3 \sim 2.30 \times 10^3$	$1.30 \times 10^3 \sim 4.13 \times 10^4$	$9.50 \times 10^6 \sim 9.50 \times 10^7$	$3.91 \times 10^{11} \sim 1.24 \times 10^{13}$	$\approx 90^\circ$	$2.87 \times 10^{-3}'' \sim 3.13 \times 10^{-4}''$
Mars	6.39×10^{23}	3.39×10^6	1R~10R	$3.55 \times 10^3 \sim 1.12 \times 10^3$	$1.52 \times 10^3 \sim 4.76 \times 10^4$	$5.41 \times 10^6 \sim 5.33 \times 10^7$	$4.57 \times 10^{11} \sim 1.43 \times 10^{13}$	$\approx 90^\circ$	$7.10 \times 10^{-4}'' \sim 7.78 \times 10^{-5}''$
Jupiter	1.90×10^{27}	7.15×10^7	1R~10R	$4.21 \times 10^4 \sim 1.33 \times 10^4$	$2.67 \times 10^3 \sim 8.44 \times 10^4$	$1.12 \times 10^8 \sim 1.12 \times 10^9$	$7.99 \times 10^{11} \sim 2.53 \times 10^{13}$	$\approx 90^\circ$	$8.20 \times 10^{-2}'' \sim 9.18 \times 10^{-3}''$
Saturn	5.68×10^{26}	6.00×10^7	1R~10R	$2.51 \times 10^4 \sim 7.95 \times 10^3$	$3.75 \times 10^3 \sim 1.19 \times 10^5$	$9.42 \times 10^7 \sim 9.46 \times 10^8$	$1.13 \times 10^{12} \sim 3.57 \times 10^{13}$	$\approx 90^\circ$	$3.03 \times 10^{-2}'' \sim 3.38 \times 10^{-3}''$
Uranus	8.68×10^{25}	2.59×10^7	1R~10R	$1.50 \times 10^4 \sim 4.73 \times 10^3$	$2.71 \times 10^3 \sim 8.59 \times 10^4$	$4.07 \times 10^7 \sim 4.06 \times 10^8$	$8.13 \times 10^{11} \sim 2.58 \times 10^{13}$	$\approx 90^\circ$	$1.13 \times 10^{-2}'' \sim 1.25 \times 10^{-3}''$
Neptune	1.03×10^{26}	2.48×10^7	1R~10R	$1.66 \times 10^4 \sim 5.26 \times 10^3$	$2.34 \times 10^3 \sim 7.40 \times 10^5$	$3.89 \times 10^7 \sim 3.89 \times 10^8$	$7.02 \times 10^{11} \sim 2.22 \times 10^{12}$	$\approx 90^\circ$	$1.39 \times 10^{-2}'' \sim 1.25 \times 10^{-3}''$
Moon	7.38×10^{22}	1.74×10^6	1R~10R	$1.68 \times 10^3 \sim 5.32 \times 10^2$	$1.63 \times 10^3 \sim 5.14 \times 10^4$	$2.73 \times 10^6 \sim 2.73 \times 10^7$	$4.88 \times 10^{11} \sim 1.54 \times 10^{12}$	$89.8^\circ \sim 87.5^\circ$	$1.41 \times 10^{-4}'' \sim 1.52 \times 10^{-5}''$

Table 4. The angle of the starlight passing around the planets and moon of the solar system calculated using classical mechanics.

4. Re-examination of the Michelson-Morley Experiment - Inadequate Experimental Conditions and Methods

The Michelson-Morley experiment employs interferometry. The interferometer used in this experiment involved a light source being emitted, split between mirrors A and B via a silvered glass plate, and then recombined. The two beams were then combined, and an observer (detector) used the phase difference to determine whether interference had occurred.[1] The fundamental premise of the Michelson-Morley experiment was that if the Earth were to move through the ether, a light medium that exists everywhere in the universe, the speed of light, whether moving in the same or different direction as the Earth, would vary depending on the direction of travel. This generates a phase difference, which allows the observation of an interference pattern. The Michelson-Morley experiment was repeated in various directions; however, not interference pattern was observed.

*The Michelson-Morley experiment appears to have overlooked two key points:

- The ether can have a mass.
- None of the matters violate the law of inertia.

The Michelson-Morley experiment was conducted in a stone cellar, free from external interference. If the ether possessed a mass, it would not violate the law of inertia (the property of an object to remain at rest or continue in uniform linear motion in the absence of an external force), making the experimental conditions too harsh to observe changes in the speed of light. Under the Michelson-Morley method, interference did not occur regardless of the direction of the experiment. The ether, possessing a mass,

remained stationary within the stone cellar without any change in its motion.

In conclusion, the Michelson-Morley method was not suitable for searching for an ether with mass.

5. Proposal of a New Experimental Method to Find the Ether

We used classical mechanics to calculate the angle of deflection of starlight passing around the sun. Calculating this angle required that the ether possesses a mass. Ether, the medium of light, must exist wherever light propagates in the universe. We now propose an experimental method to be conducted on Earth's surface to find the ether. [8]

*Premise

- The ether must possess mass.
- Ether must exist on the Earth's surface, like the atmosphere.

*We compare and measure the interference patterns by varying the two conditions below.

-One method uses the interference pattern generated when two light beams that have traveled different distances in a stationary atmosphere, unaffected by external forces, strike a single point.

-The other method measures the interference pattern generated when two light beams travel different distances at a location where the wind blows perpendicular to the direction of light propagation.

*The experimental method to find the ether is as follows:

- 1) Conduct the experiment indoors or in a windless location using artificial wind.

Figure 3) Indoors, light source A moves across a reflective mirror at a constant distance to reach observer B. Compare the changes in the interference patterns generated by light sources A and A' with and without artificial wind.

2) As shown in Figure 3, the light projected from light source A moves through the airspace between the reflective mirrors to reach observer B.

3) Light source A' is projected onto observer B near the location where it A will reach observer B.

4) The distance between light source A' and observer B is short compared to the travel distance of light source A, such that the interference pattern will be minimally affected regardless of the wind.

5) The interference patterns generated by light sources A and A' were measured by observer B.

6) The interference patterns generated by light sources A and A' in the absence of wind as A and A' reference point were compared and analyzed with the interference patterns generated by light sources A and A' in the presence of wind.

7) Mirrors that reflect each other are used to increase the distance light can travel.

8) The mirrors must be securely and stably fixed to prevent wind and other external influences from interfering with the observation of light interference pattern.

9) Examples of lasers used as light sources include a short-wavelength excimer laser (wavelength 193 nm) and a visible-light helium-neon laser (wavelength 632 nm).

10) The interferometer used in the experiment should have a sensitivity of approximately 10^{-12} m/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$.

11) Mirrors are placed facing each other at a fixed distance (D1).

12) The two mirrors are perpendicular to the surfaces and reflect each other regularly.

13) Light source A is illuminated at a fixed angle (θ) on mirror a, and it bounces back and forth with mirror b, reaching observer B. At this time, light source A' was projected onto observer B, and the interference pattern between light sources A and A' was measured.

-Without artificial wind: In an indoor or windless environment, the wavelength of the light emitted by source A upon reaching observer B was measured. Light source A' directs light toward observer B, and the interference pattern formed by sources A and A' is measured to define the reference point.

-With artificial wind: Under conditions identical to those without artificial airflow, an artificial wind of speed v is introduced perpendicular to the direction of propagation of round-trip light source A. The wavelength of the light reaching observer B from source A was measured. Light source A' directed light toward observer B, and the interference pattern formed by sources A and A' was measured.

14) The interference pattern measured in the absence of artificial wind were compared with the reference point.

The number of interference patterns (ΔN) is given by

$$\Delta N = \frac{\Delta D}{\lambda} \quad (27)$$

where ΔD is the distance in wavelengths and λ is the wavelength. In Figure 3), the number of interference patterns (ΔN) between the two light wavelengths when the light source moves along paths A→B and A'→B in the absence of artificial wind was used as a reference point. The average speed of the artificial wind affecting light source A moving back and forth is v . To maintain the average speed of the artificial wind, if technical constraints exist, its speed and position of the artificial wind can be varied. When light source A moves along path A→B, the distance traveled along path A→B is varied to ensure that the number of interference fringes (ΔN) is accurately derived from the time difference (Δt) between observer B when the wind is blowing and when it is not. c is the speed of light, and λ is the wavelength of light.

Figure 4) (a) D1R is the one-way distance traveled by light source A from mirror b to mirror a without any external influence. (b) D is the total distance traveled by light source A without any external influence. DW is the total distance traveled by the wind. DR is the total distance traveled by light source A owing to external influence (wind). Here, the travel times (t) of D, DW, and DR were identical.

In Figure 4) (a), D1R is the one-way distance traveled by light source A from mirror b to mirror a without any external influence. In Figure 4) (b), D is the total distance traveled by light source A without external influence. DW is the total distance traveled by the wind. DR is the total distance traveled by light source A owing to external influence (wind). Here, the travel times (t) of D, DW, and DR were identical. The equation for calculating the distance difference ΔD between the DR and D is as follows. The equation below was derived from Figure 4) (a).

$$D1R = \sqrt{D1^2 + (S/2)^2} \quad (28)$$

Here, D1R is the one-way distance traveled by light source A from mirror b to mirror a without external influence, D1 is the distance between the mirrors, and S is the distance between the arrival points of light source A when it travels back and forth between mirrors a and b.

$$t = \frac{D}{c} \quad (29)$$

Here, D is the total distance traveled by light source A at the speed of light c at time t without any external influence.

$$DW = vt \quad (30)$$

Where DW is the total distance traveled by the wind at wind speed v at time t. The following equation was derived from Figure 4) (b).

$$DR = \sqrt{D^2 + DW^2} \quad (31)$$

Here, DR is the total distance traveled by light source A owing to the external influence (wind). The distance difference between the DR and D, ΔD , is expressed by the following equation.

$$\Delta D = DR - D \quad (32)$$

*This is an example calculation based on the experimental conditions.

The distance D1 between the mirrors is 50 m, the distance E between the light source A and the observer B is 40 m, and the distance S between the arrival points when the light source A goes back and forth between mirror a and mirror b is 0.01 m (1 cm, angle of light source A : $\theta \approx 0.005729578^\circ$). If E is 40 m, then the total number of round trips is 4,000. To find the distance of D1R in Figure 3), using Equation (28), D1R was determined to be 50.00000025 m. If light source A moves back and forth from mirror a to mirror b without any external influence, the total travel distance D is 50.00000025 m \times 4,000 times \times 2 = 400,000.002 m (400.000002 km). When the average wind speed v = 5 m/s and D is 400,000.002 m (400.000002 km), the time (t) for the light to travel distance D is 0.0013333 s using Equation (29). The distance DW traveled by the wind that affects the direction of movement of light source A when it moves is 0.0066666 m using Equation (30). Now, we can find the distance (DR) that light source A actually travels owing to external influences. The DR is 400,000.00200000004 m using Equation (31), and the distance difference (ΔD) between DR and D is 0.00000000004 m (4×10^{-2} nm) using Equation (32). When the light source was an excimer laser with a short wavelength of 193 nm, the number of interference patterns (ΔN) of the light source was 0.0002, and when the light source was a laser wavelength of 632 nm, the number of interference patterns (ΔN) was 0.000063.

The distance between the mirrors (D1), the distance between the light source A and observer B (E), and the distance between the arrival points when going back and forth between mirrors a and b must be appropriately considered according to the actual experiment. It is not easy to precisely align the mirrors so that they reflect regularly and to stably fix the mirrors so that they do not affect the wavelength of light. To find the ether, the distance between the mirrors (D1), the distance between the light source A and

observer B (E), and the distance between the arrival points when going back and forth between mirrors a and b (S) were varied, and the number of interference fringes (ΔN) at that time was calculated.

D1(m)	E(m)	S(m)	D(m)	v(m/s)	ΔD (nm)	ΔN (Light 193 nm)	ΔN (Light 632 nm)
50	40	0.01	400,000.002	5	4×10^{-2}	0.0002	0.000063
20	500	0.01	2,000,000.062499999	15	1	0.0052	0.0016
50	200	0.01	2,000,000.01	15	2.3	0.012	0.0036
100	100	0.01	2,000,000.0025	15	2.5	0.013	0.004
200	200	0.01	8,000,000.0024	15	11	0.057	0.017
200	200	0.005	16,000,000.00125	15	21	0.109	0.033

Table 5. Shows the number of interference patterns (ΔN) calculated when variables such as the distance between mirrors (D1), the distance between light source A and observer B (E), and the distance between arrival points when moving back and forth between mirrors (s) are changed.

The wavelengths of the laser light source were 193 and 632 nm respectively. The values used in the calculations were as follows.

- 1) Distance between mirrors (D1): 20 m to 200 m
- 2) Distance (E) between light source (A) and observer (A'): 40 to 500 m
- 3) Distance traveled by light (D): Approximately 400,000 m (400 km) to 16,000,000 m (16,000 km)
- 4) Wind speed (v): 5 m/s to 15 m/s
- 5) Distance between arrival points of light traveling back and forth between mirrors a and b (S): 0.005 m to 0.01 m

When the wavelength of the light source was 193 nm, the number of interference fringes (ΔN) was calculated as 0.0002 to 0.109. When the wavelength of the light source was 632 nm, the number of interference fringes (ΔN) was calculated as 0.000063 to 0.033. The larger the number of interference particles (ΔN), the easier it is to detect the interference patterns. If interference patterns appear, this will be an experimental result confirming on Earth the ether with the desired mass. For reference, variables D1 and E applied to the experimental data above are for an interferometer with a sensitivity of approximately $10^{-12} \text{ m}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$. A higher sensitivity facilitates interference pattern measurement. If we were to use the Michelson interferometer (sensitivity: $10^{-21} \text{ m}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$), which was used to detect gravitational waves, we would expect interference patterns to be easily detected even with much smaller values for variables D1 and W. [9]

Conclusion: Under the assumption that the ether has mass, even when an external force (wind: 5 m/s to 15 m/s) is applied, the propagation distance of light must be in the range of approximately 400 km to 16,000 km for the interference fringes to be measurable.

6. The ether is likely dark matter.

We propose a similarity between dark matter, which accounts for a portion of the total mass of the universe, and ether, which serves as a medium for the light propagation. Dark matter, a form of matter with mass, is essential for understanding the structure of the universe and rotational dynamics of galaxies [9,10,11,12,13,14].

If the mass is attributed to ether, it is expected that ether could become a suitable substance capable of explaining the fundamental properties of dark matter.

- 1) It exists throughout the universe wherever light (electromagnetic waves) propagates.

2) Because it possesses mass, it can account for phenomena such as galactic rotation speeds and gravitational lensing.

3) As a medium for the propagation of light (electromagnetic waves), they are not directly observable.

7. Conclusion

We have argued that the deflection angle of starlight passing near the sun, as predicted by Einstein's general theory of relativity, is inconsistent with the observational data obtained during solar eclipses from 1919 to 1954 (the observed deflection angles at perihelion distances of $2R$ (1.4×10^9 m) to $10R$ (7×10^9 m) ranged from $2.73''$ to $0.93''$, whereas the angles calculated using Einstein's equation ranged from $0.87''$ to $0.17''$). In contrast, we accurately calculated the deflection angle of the starlight using classical mechanics (the classical values at perihelion distances of $2R$ (1.40×10^9 m) to $10R$ (7.00×10^9 m) range from $3.50''$ to $0.77''$), which are nearly identical to the observed values of $2.73''$ to $0.93''$.

We have also shown that the Michelson–Morley experimental method is not suitable for detecting an ether that with a mass. Assuming that the ether has mass, we propose a new experimental method for its detection on Earth. Even when an external force (wind: 5 m/s to 15 m/s) is applied to the atmosphere containing ether, the propagation distance of light must be in the range of approximately 400 km to 16,000 km for interference fringes to be measurable.

We believe that an ether with mass can explain many unresolved problems in the universe, including dark matter.

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